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A past not yet passed: Postmemory in the work of Mona Hatoum

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A PAST NOT YET PASSED: POSTMEMORY IN THE WORK OF MONA HATOUM

‘What I, as the daughter of someone who lived through the Nakba learned...was that for Palestinians, both memory and Postmemory have a special valence because the past is not yet passed.’

- Lila Abu-Lughod

‘A man [shot] a bullet into the neck of my sister Salhiyeh who was nine months pregnant. Then he cut her stomach open with a butcher's knife.’

- Testimony of Ms. Haleem Eid, 30: Survivor of the *Deir Yassin* massacre

Mona Hatoum is one of the most internationally recognized and acclaimed Palestinian artists working today. Born in Lebanon and residing in the United Kingdom since 1975 (when she was unable to return to her home following the outbreak of the Lebanese civil war), Hatoum’s oeuvre is marked not only by her personal experience of exile but also by the collective Palestinian experience of dispossession and occupation. Although it is clear that Hatoum’s work deals with what can be described as the ongoing ‘Nakbaization’ facing Palestinians, the artist does so while actively evading didactic political narration. Yet, beneath the deliberate political opacity of her work, one can find traces of a form of ‘postmemory’ particular to the Palestinian experience. Evidence of postmemory can be found in many works from across Hatoum’s career, and can be

in turn seen as central to her emphasis on the broader issues of trauma, gender, orality and corporeality.

Used to describe the relationship to the personal, collective and cultural trauma of previous generations, postmemory is characterised by a transmission of memory from previous generations that is invested in and experienced so closely by a subsequent generation that these memories seem to constitute personal memories in their own right.ⁱ Hatoum's work can be argued to exhibit the presence of postmemory because it is shaped by the memory of critical events in Palestinian history that the artist did not experience directly. The relationship between Mona Hatoum's work and postmemory can be seen perhaps most clearly in her now iconic piece, *Measures of Distance* (1988).

Measures of Distance is one of Hatoum's most well known works and is notable for operating in the interstice between film, art and the documentary, thus making it the subject of analysis by scholars across various disciplines.ⁱⁱ Based on a series of letters between the artist and her mother, the work explores the consequences of exile on multiple generations of Palestinian women while challenging audiences to revise their assumptions around Palestinian identity and experience. A transfixing and repetitive work, the piece focuses on the testimonies of the artist and her mother while raising questions about the im/possibility of the narration of trauma and encouraging a spectatorial activity that draws attention to the inability to close the traumatic gaps generated by exile.ⁱⁱⁱ

The fifteen-minute video is a touching portrayal of Hatoum and her mother's experience of exile and involves scrolling Arabic text superimposed over the naked

figure of the artist's mother. The text consisting of letters reflecting the pain of exile from Hatoum's mother is read aloud by the artist, creating a fluid connection between the story and narration of both mother and daughter. The work also includes two overlapping soundtracks; the first a conversation between mother and daughter and the second an English translation and narration of her mother's letters by the artist. The visual distance between mother and daughter created by the scrolling fragmented text as well as the disorientating overlapping soundtrack, serve to reinforce an overriding sense of distance not only between Hatoum and her subject, but also with us as the audience.

The impact of exile, displacement and the experience of postmemory in *Measures of Distance* is perhaps nowhere more clearly articulated than in the section of the video where Hatoum translates a letter from her mother that reads:

'Can you imagine us having to separate from all our loved ones, leaving everything behind and starting again from scratch, our family scattered all over the world...And now that you and your sisters have left Lebanon, you are again living in another exile and in a culture that is totally different to your own. So, when you talk about a feeling of fragmentation and not knowing where you really belong, well, that has been the painful reality of all our people.'^{iv}

The act of narrating her mothers experience exposes an experience of postmemory by collapsing the divide between author and subject. As it remains unclear who is telling 'their' story and therefore to whom the story belongs, the piece suggests both explicitly and implicitly that the memory and experience of exile is shared by both mother and daughter. This reinforces Leila Abu Lughod's suggestion that the exile brought about as a consequence of the *Nakba* is a history not yet passed for the

generations of Palestinians born after the *Nakba*. Put differently, the artist's experience of a double exile is indicative of Abu-Lughod's suggestion that Palestinian offspring carry not only the surrogate postmemory recollections of their parents, but also experience the consequences of these memories directly in their own reality.

Measures of Distance thus draws attention both to the shared points of connection in the experiences of both mother and daughter (and two generations) but also the multitude of distances between mother and daughter, including story telling and narration, history and the present, writing and reading, Arabic and English, subject and artist. The scrolling Arabic text in the video is also reminiscent of barbed wire separating the bodies of mother and daughter and insinuates a sense of distance created with threat. This allusion to a corporeal peril created by lines of separative wire is reminiscent of Hatoum's well known work *Homebound* (2000) where the audience is separated from a domestic environment, albeit a threatening *unheimlich* one, by threads of wire cables. Jill Bennett explains the breed of installation seen in *Homebound* 'facilitates the carryover of an affective response from one piece to another; Hatoum's incarcerative space engenders a certain bodily response...[where] one is effectively assisted in a process of embodied perception.'^v The utilisation of traumatic memory and experience and its facilitation in works of art by Hatoum, serve to create an 'empathic connection' between artwork and audience.^{vi} As one views *Measures of Distance* from the perspective of the camera, and as a consequence the viewpoint of Hatoum, the audience is implicated in the intimate space captured and created by the work. One is thus, empathically caught in the intimate space between mother and daughter. The separations between subject and artist; whether semantic, bodily, or visual, serve to

highlight the notion that it is exile that binds Hatoum and her mother in *Measures of Distance*.^{vii}

The intimacy in *Measures of Distance* is further facilitated by the naked figure of Hatoum's mother. The naked body of the mother, an older Palestinian woman, brings to the work a series of Western conceptions of gender and sexuality ascribed to Middle Eastern women. In recent years the Western gaze has focused its attention on issues of gender in the work of female Middle Eastern artists. Importantly, this is an oversimplification of gender roles in the Middle East and is a projection of Western Feminist ideology on the Arabic Other. Although Hatoum's work is notable for engaging with issues of gender more broadly (and much has been written about her work in this regard) it is vital to at least briefly consider how the representation of women in the history of Palestinian cultural output impacts upon the reading and analysis of Hatoum's work.^{viii}

As Amal Amireh notes, in the Palestinian national narrative, Palestine is metamorphosed as a woman and an abundance of Palestinian literature uses the metaphor of the woman as a symbol of Palestine. This is most clearly seen in the work of the national poet of Palestine Mahmoud Darwish and his well-known poem, *A Lover from Palestine*. The Western essentialising perception of Middle Eastern women does not allow for the culturally diverse roles and perceptions of women in various Middle Eastern cultures. In the case of Palestinian women, this consideration disavows the specific significance of women's story telling and the symbol of the female body as a metaphor for the land of Palestine. It is therefore significant that in *Measures of Distance* the mother's naked figure is literally layered with stories of exile and the

effects of the *Nakba*. The naked female figure in *Measures of Distance*, is thus utilised twice as the nexus between Mona Hatoum and the Palestinian homeland. The artist's mother is her conduit to the experience of the *Nakba*, and historical Palestine, as well as a more universal Palestinian symbol of the lost homeland.

The emphasis upon both testimony and memory in *Measures of Distance* signals a central concern evident in Palestinian cultural production more broadly where the dispossession and exile brought by the foundation of Israel is highlighted as an ongoing event – a past not yet passed. The ongoing experience of occupation and exile is represented by artists not only through the use archival history but also through an exploration of the role of memory as a tool in the validation and verification of experience. Edward Said explains that images associated with memory and aspiration, are for Palestinians often the only symbolic substitute for their citizenship or relationship to place.^{ix} Images are thus invested in as tools of historical, political and cultural confirmation. As a language comprised of images, Palestinian visual art (along with other forms of art) is a crucial vehicle for not only the representation of the Palestinian experience but also a verification of it. As Palestinian archival history has been placed in a subordinate position to that of the Jewish experience, and its documentation appears scant in comparison to the 'monolith' of Jewish history, memory and the oral tradition are often the most relied upon conduits of history.^xAs can be evidenced in the refugee camp art of the years following *Al-Nakba*, memory is a potent force in the facilitation of Palestinian art practice.^{xi} For the generations following the Catastrophe, the *Nakba* was not directly experienced yet the after effects of the

event continue to shape their everyday existence and as a result the events often manifest themselves in contemporary Palestinian art.

POSTMEMORY AND THE NAKBA

It is without a doubt that the events of the *Nakba* play a paramount role in the collective memory of Palestinians. However, as a theoretical and analytical framework, collective memory with its associations to nationalism and its frequent affiliation and manipulation as a tool of propaganda, is not a sufficient term or frame to describe the nuances and potency of memory in the Palestinian discourse. It is precisely the essentialising character of collective memory that renders it unable to suitably describe the Palestinian association to memory. The presence of memory in Palestinian art is not merely bound to the collective or shared consciousness model of recollection found in collective memory. Collective memory in Palestinian art requires a more refined framework; one that is inclusive not only of the collective and often essentialising experience, but one that is also subsumes personal memory. It is the notion of postmemory that accommodates the personal association to collective recollection and is thus a more refined concept; one that is more suitable to the Palestinian understanding of memory.

The concept of postmemory is founded on Kaja Silverman's notion of heteropathic recollection. Silverman's theory is based on the concept that one is able to carry surrogate memories of another through a process of heteropathic identification; creating a method and relationship where an individual takes on to his or herself the

memories of another.^{xiii} Marianne Hirsch has elaborated on the concept of heteropathic recollection with the ensuing model of postmemory. Hirsch describes this model of memory as being a departure from preconceived ideas of memory and history as a result of its basis in generational distance and deep personal connection. She elaborates by explaining that ‘postmemory characterizes the experience of those who grow up dominated by narratives that preceded their birth, whose belated stories are evoked by the stories of the previous generation shaped by traumatic events that can be neither understood nor recreated.’^{xiii}

Lila Abu-Lughod’s statement that postmemory has a special valence for Palestinians reassesses the parameters of Hirsch’s postmemory model that relies heavily on the idea of a disparity between the experience of Holocaust trauma survivors and their children. Hirsch’s model cannot adhere to the contemporary Palestinian experience, as post-*Nakba* offspring are themselves subject to the ongoing trauma that has arisen as a result of the Catastrophe. Consequently, postmemory in the Palestinian experience is not only grounded in the surrogate memories of the Catastrophe but is also carried over into the contemporary experience of exile and dispossession. Memory in effect transcends generational and historical divides and makes its way into the present as a living history.^{xiv} The children of the survivors of the *Nakba* can be argued to experience an everyday reality that is overshadowed by the memory of a much significant past lived through by their parents, comparable to the children of Holocaust survivors.^{xv}

The presence of postmemory in the work of Mona Hatoum, particularly in artworks with reference to the repercussions and memories of the *Nakba*, can be said to

exemplify traumatic memory. The differentiation between traumatic and narrative memory is a noteworthy one. Traumatic memory breaks the ongoing narrative and in so doing severs connections between the past, the present and future.^{xvi} The psychology of trauma argues widely that the clear linear narration of one's traumatic memories is a significant step in the process of recovery. This process of transformation from traumatic to linear memory is reliant on an audience.

Traumatic memory's lack of a coherent sequential order is reminiscent of Edward Said's anxiety concerning the Palestinian story's lack of a coherent, beginning, middle and end. As a history that is to a large extent oral, and whose primary reference is traumatic memory, Palestinian history has an analogous configuration to traumatic memory, one absent of chronological succession. Susan Brison's explanation of traumatic memory's reliance on an appreciative audience is also a notion that resonates with Said. An accepting appreciative audience is akin to a sense of acknowledgment. If an appreciative audience is suggested as a facilitating agent in overcoming trauma, this perhaps explains the popular assertion that violence and suffering will not cease for Palestinians until there has been an acknowledgment of their suffering.^{xvii}

In contrast to traumatic memory, narrative memory is characterised by an individual's control over their memory and the recounting of their experience. In other words, it 'is not passively endured; rather it is an act on the part of the narrator, a speech act that defuses traumatic memory, giving shape and temporal order to the events recalled...'^{xviii} If one is to accept Brison's distinction between traumatic and narrative memory, her characterization resonates with models of memory transmission, employed by Mona Hatoum. In effect one can come to understand that the modes of

memory recounting the *Nakba* and the process of exile utilised by Mona Hatoum as defined by traumatic memory.

The memory and postmemory of the *Nakba* is of paramount importance in Palestinian history as a result of the absence of archival history on the subject. The destruction of the Palestinian presence in historical Palestine and the Zionist ethos that disavows their existence entirely, serve to further the reliance on memory and postmemory as validation of the Palestinian presence and experience. Mahmoud Darwish describes Palestine, writing that ‘we are a country of words’.^{xix} Darwish here states that Palestine and *Palestinianess* is comprised of words and not the land itself nor text or visual forms. Here Darwish clearly tells us that historical Palestine exists in the oral tradition. With the lack of archival and institutional presence, it is the oral tradition, a tradition bound to memory, that records, interprets and disseminates history.

The division of modes of memory between narrative and traumatic memory is one that is concomitant to the differences in emphasis found in the traditional Palestinian story telling distinctions between the *hikayat* and the *qissa*. Oral history in traditional Palestinian culture is distributed on the basis of gender. The *hikayat* is traditionally the female domain, one that has a particular focus on fables and folk tales. This type of story telling is based on accounts of real happenings, either in history or in the speaker’s experience but is prone to exaggeration and sentimentality. The *hikayat* stands in contrast to the *qissa*, and is traditionally often referred to by males as *kizb*, or lies.^{xx} The *qissa* is a linear narrative form of story telling, one more akin to our Western conventional conception of the historical discourse. History or *al tarikh* is a discourse traditionally associated with a male teller. Under such a framework, as Susan

Slyomovics explains, ‘counter-commentary’ and ‘questions and oppositions become the domain of female utterance’. As a result, the male voice is a conduit of official history, whilst the female voice is relegated to a reactive role; challenging official and archival history. Slyomovics goes further, referencing Mikhail Bakhtin’s suggestion that hierarchies are intrinsic to language. As Bakhtin notes, the authoritative is a ‘prior discourse’, one that is supported and maintained by the political, legal and moral authorities that dominate public activities. In the case of Palestine, males are supported by what Bakhtin describes as the ‘prior discourse’.^{xxi} They are conduits of what is seen as official history, while women, associated with domestic and oral history are seen as separate to political history.

The divide in emphasis between the *qissa* and the *hikayat* is in cause and effect a differentiation between the processes of oral and archival history. One must understand that oral history shares the importance of narrative and archival history and both are equally plagued with historical inaccuracy. Beyond existing in a dialectical relationship constantly competing for historical legitimacy, oral and archival history are also heavily reliant and one and other. It can be said that history ‘need not be opposed to witness memories; rather, memory is a source for, indeed it propels, history by instigating the inquiry...’^{xxii}

The co-existence of *hikayat* and *qissa* history is woven into the fabric of Palestinian history, culture and collective understanding. The most recognisable persona of the Palestinian resistance and strive toward nationhood, is that of Yassir Arafat. As a leader of the Palestinian people, Yassir Arafat’s almost permanent donning of the distinct *keffieh* cloth meant that it became an icon of *Palestinianess*.^{xxiii}

Traditionally a symbol of masculinity the black and white *keffieh* has since the 1970s become increasingly divorced from its gendered role.^{xxiv} As a symbol of the Palestinian liberation movement the inclusion of the *keffieh* in the work of Mona Hatoum is the most overt reference to the artist's cultural heritage to be found in her entire oeuvre.

Hatoum's *Keffieh* work comprised of human hair on cotton, was created between 1993 and 1999. Upon first glance the work appears to be a traditional Palestinian *keffieh* yet with closer inspection one swiftly notices strands of female human hair protruding from the cloth's boundary. The black and white cotton cloth is comprised of a simple black border woven with cotton into the textile. The human hair not only extends beyond the border of the textile itself, but is also woven into the cloth to comprise the organic wave and fence like shapes found in the inner *keffieh*. The female hair feminizes this traditionally masculine nationalist symbol. Homi Bhabha notes that the metonym of the female body embroidered into the fabric of *Keffieh* exposes the masculine nationalist symbol as one that directs its aggression both internally and externally. He explains that the macho style directs its aggression internally and is 'poised against the presence and participation of women, whose voices are repressed or sublimated in the cause of the struggle.'^{xxv} For Bhabha, the artist's feminized headscarf is an act of re-insertion of the place of women in the nationalist struggle.

The use of hair in *Keffieh* may also be understood as a comment on the story telling role of women in Palestinian culture. All linear shapes in Hatoum's cloth are woven with cotton into the textile and are securely placed within the cloth. It is the more organic shapes that are embroidered in female hair. The textile is of such thin

cotton that visible beneath its surface are the clumps of female hair at the ends of the embroidery work. One might align Hatoum's decision to allow unruly hair to protrude from the boundaries of the cloth and to embroider with hair only the organic shapes in *Keffieh*, as an allusion to the female Palestinian storytelling of the nationalist struggle. The unruly hair embroidery stands in contrast to the linear cotton weave of *Keffieh*. This contrast can be related to the traditional distinction between *hikayat* and *qissa* story telling. It is narrative linear history that is fixed and firmly woven into history and ideology, and it is the personal and traumatic memory of women that lurks beneath the surface. Such an analysis is in keeping with Bhabha's interpretation of the *Keffieh* work as one that highlights the sublimated voice and participation of women in the Palestinian struggle. ^{xxvi}

With the exception of the *Keffieh* work, Mona Hatoum has since the early 1990s increasingly disassociated herself from any overt references to her cultural background and the Palestinian struggle. ^{xxvii} The departure from explicit associations to her 'Palestinianess' is cited by Hatoum as being instigated by the completion of *Measures of Distance*. The work signalled a moment of catharsis for Hatoum and she claims that after its completion she felt a burden being lifted for she could, in her own words, 'get on with other kinds of work, where every work did not necessarily have to tell the whole story, where I could just deal with one little aspect of my experience'. ^{xxviii}

'POSTMEMBERING' DEIR YASSIN

Although Hatoum's oeuvre is both too rich and diverse for works to be looked at simply through the prism of her Palestinian background, it is crucial to understand the signifiers in her work that relate directly to events in Palestinian history. Of particular interest is the way in which many of her works refer to the narrative of the village named *Deir Yassin*. Although *Deir Yassin* is but one example of over four hundred villages depopulated and destroyed with the foundation of Israel, it remains as an emblematic event of the *Nakba*.

Destroyed by Zionist forces in 1948, *Deir Yassin* is at the centre of Palestinian collective memory of *Al-Nakba* and in the last seven decades has been invested in as a symbol of the Palestinian experience of the Zionist occupation. Moreover, it is often cited by Palestinians as the event that instigated the mass exodus of 1948 and the consequent occupation of historical Palestine.^{xxix} *Deir Yassin* can therefore be interpreted as a collective memory lens into the events of *Al-Nakba*. The fixation on the historical events of *Deir Yassin* by both Palestinians and Israelis, signifies the fact that the village itself has become bait in the ideological and propaganda campaign of both Arabs and Israelis.^{xxx} In 1948, both sides, Zionist and Arab, exaggerated the events of the *Deir Yassin* massacre for their own propagandistic purposes. For the Zionists, the massacre and capture of *Deir Yassin* signified the strength of their military and was publicised throughout the Palestinian population to incite an exodus and fear of Zionist forces. Their exaggerations were also mirrored by the Palestinians, who at the time numbered the dead at anywhere between 200 and 350 inhabitants to encourage international sympathy for their plight.^{xxxi} *Deir Yassin* was not an isolated event or attack, but is merely the most notorious and well documented of the 1948 massacres of

Palestinians by Zionist forces.^{xxxii} News of the massacre and of the occupation of *Deir Yassin* spread throughout Arab communities like wildfire. Menachim Begin, former Israeli Prime Minister and leader of the Irgun forces who lead the attack on *Deir Yassin* writes:

‘Arabs throughout the country, induced to believe wild tales of ‘Irgun butchery’ were seized with limitless panic and started to flee for their lives. This mass flight soon developed into a maddened, uncontrollable stampede.’^{xxxiii}

The stories of ‘Irgun butchery’ cited by Menachin Begin located their focal point on Zionist attacks against women. Frances Hasso writes about the effects of gender politics in the 1948 Zionist victory, by citing Ted Swedenberg’s analysis that honour was for Palestinians intimately related to both the possession of land and the maintenance of kin women’s virginity or exclusive sexual availability.^{xxxiv} The exaggerated reports of *Deir Yassin* focused on the brutality toward pregnant women, often claiming that they had been sliced open, disembowelled and thrown into wells.^{xxxv} These reports have now been documented in research and archival projects such as *Deir Yassin Remembered* that chronicles the individual testimonies of the massacre, including that of Haleem Eid who witnessed the disembowelment of her pregnant sister.^{xxxvi} Importantly, the sexual and physical attacks at *Deir Yassin* can be argued to have been acts of deliberate psychological warfare by the Zionist forces, as they were aware that such attacks on women would spread fear amongst the local population.^{xxxvii}

Though the stories of brutality that occurred in *Deir Yassin* are disseminated through oral history, *Deir Yassin* is exceptional in that only 4 of its 144 houses were destroyed in 1948. The village itself is still largely intact and is now located in the Har

Nof district of West Jerusalem and has been converted into an Israeli mental hospital. *Deir Yassin* has, however problematically, achieved a place in archival history. A covering up of the massacre was impossible, as reports of the killings surfaced immediately.^{xxxviii} As such, the village is an exception amongst villages depopulated in 1948, who in contrast to *Deir Yassin*, rely almost exclusively on oral history to record the events and experiences of the *Nakba*. It is fitting that *Deir Yassin*, a place that remains emblematic of the Palestinian experience of the *Nakba*, repeatedly finds its way into the work of Hatoum who is arguably the most well known Palestinian artist in the international art world. Rather than focus on the archival documents and history of the village however, the references to *Deir Yassin* in Hatoum's work rely instead on the transmission of a traumatic postmemory.

In the aftermath of the Sabra and Shatila massacres on Palestinian refugees in 1982 during the Lebanese civil war, the artist recounted a dream relating to the *Nakba* and the massacre of *Deir Yassin*. She describes the dream saying;

'I went to Beirut looking for my parents and in the wreckage of their home I found two plastic boxes – a pink one and a blue one. I opened the blue box and it was full of tiny toy soldiers that exploded out into the air around me becoming a cloud of flies that took on the shape of a black gravestone – 'We were only obeying orders!' I heard them say... When I turned back to the pink box, the lid was open disgorging human entrails in an endless stream. I heard my mother's voice saying, 'They were disembowelling pregnant women, that's why we had to leave.'^{xxxix}

The blue and pink boxes of Hatoum's dream are representative of a gendered Palestinian differentiation as to the reasons for the 1948 mass exodus. The pink box, one might understand as being symbolic of the female experience. It is significant that Hatoum claims to have had this dream at the time of the Lebanese civil war. Her own

experience of violence, oppression and massacre of Palestinians, is indicated through this dream to be subconsciously bound to the events of the *Nakba*. This collapsed connection between the *Nakba*, and contemporary events experienced by the artist are indicative of Postmemory. The trauma of the *Nakba* passed down through her parents and in the case of her dream, literally residing with them, is carried over into her own experience. Thus, as Lila Abu-Lughod suggests, as a Palestinian, Mona Hatoum's cultural past, is not yet passed and its trauma carries itself into the present. The Postmemory trauma of *Deir Yassin* is one that is frequently evidenced and referenced in Hatoum's art. The most obvious of such references are her works *The Negotiating Table* from 1983, *Socle du Monde* from 1992-1993 and *Entrails Carpet* from 1995.

Hatoum describes the Israeli invasion and the attacks on refugees in camps during the Lebanese civil war as the most shattering experience of her life. It was in response to the events of that war, that the artist conceived of and performed her 1983 work *The Negotiating Table*.^{x1} Performed five times, the performance consisted of Hatoum lying motionless on a table with empty chairs on either side. The artist's body was covered in beef entrails, bloodstained, wrapped in plastic and her head covered in surgical gauze whilst talks of peace by Western leaders and reports of the events of the war were playing in the background.

The juxtaposition between the media reports of the events, the peace discussions by Western leaders and the seemingly brutalised body of Mona Hatoum, highlighted the chasm between the physical experiences of war and brutality, and those that are reported and discussed. It is here, that the artist's decision to use animal entrails becomes a point of significant import. Hatoum's recounting of her dream of *Deir*

Yassin, and her mention of entrails was made within the same year the artist performed *The Negotiating Table*. Beyond being an indication of her Postmemory of the *Nakba*, references to the haunting nightmares of *Deir Yassin* in *The Negotiating Table* bring to the surface issues surrounding the controversy between archival and oral accounts of the massacre. The disembowelment of women at *Deir Yassin* features prominently in oral history of the massacre and is almost entirely absent in archival accounts of the event.^{xli}

The visual references to the massacre of *Deir Yassin* become less invested with political rhetoric and obvious allusions to Palestinian history in the latter years of Hatoum's oeuvre. The departure from overt political reference and rhetoric coincides with Hatoum's conscious move to do so after the completion of *Measures of Distance*. Nonetheless, when one becomes aware of the significance of the imagery of entrails and their reference to *Deir Yassin*, Hatoum's recurrent employment of them begins to take on a different significance. One might take the example of the *Entrails Carpet*, a work from 1995. In contrast to the literal use of entrails in *The Negotiating Table*, the artist's use of the entrails motif in her carpet is done so in silicone rubber. Despite the abandonment of real entrails, the silicone substitutes in *Entrails Mat* still provoke the same visceral response in the viewer. This response is promoted by a sense of shock when one looks closer at the mat, or indeed at the title, and the luminous mat is transformed into an object of repulse.

The emphasis on materiality in the work is also significant as silicone is now a medium we associate with the imitation of the real. It makes sense as a progression for Hatoum, when abandoning performance and the use of real entrails to choose silicon,

the closest artificial medium, as her substitute for real entrails. Frozen in their ‘plastic stillness’ the entrails in the artist’s mat are transparent.^{xliii} The audience cannot look through them directly to the ground below the mat. Our glimpse of the ground beneath the carpet and the floor beneath us, is veiled by undulating curved entrails. Thus they become the lens with which we see the ground beneath us. To choose a carpet covered in entrails, is to suggest that they literally sit on the surface and the place in which we find our grounding and our foundations; our home. Hatoum’s recounting of her dream involving entrails takes place in her parent’s home in her place of birth, Lebanon. The *unheimlich* response triggered by a domestic object in *Entrails Carpet*, this may be understood as an allusion to the presence of the story of *Deir Yassin* in Hatoum’s home.

The entrails motif also finds itself in Hatoum’s work *Socle du Monde*, a large Minimalist cube that references Piero Manzoni’s influential work of the same title from 1961. *Socle du Monde*, translates to ‘pedestal of the world’ and as such Manzoni’s 1961 version of the work, a sculpture or pedestal placed outside, is suggestive of the notion that everything in the world, all vegetative, animal and mineral forms, are a work of art. The line between what constitutes the work of art, and what structures support or influence it, become bound in Manzoni’s work. Hatoum’s appropriation of *Socle du Monde* is covered in iron fillings that are evocative of entrails. Hatoum’s work suggests that her foundation, or pedestal of the world, is literally covered in entrails. As we have come to understand, for Mona Hatoum, entrails are a reference to *Deir Yassin* and it is *Deir Yassin* that is cited, in her 1982 dream, to be the instigator of exodus. As exile can be described to be the determining state of being in the Palestinian experience and therefore their world, it is reasonable that Mona Hatoum chooses the motif of

entrails to cover her pedestal to the world. For in doing so, she suggests that her world literally has its foundations in exile. If we are to accept the analysis that Manzoni's work binds the work of art to its influences in the world, then Hatoum's version takes on a new meaning. *Socle du Monde* exemplifies Hatoum's perception of the 'entire world as foreign land'.^{xliii}

The historical debate surrounding the massacre of *Deir Yassin*, and the various attempts at creating a memorial museum commemorating the event are indicative of the Palestinian anxiety toward archival historical presence.^{xliv} Mona Hatoum's works *Self-Erasing Drawing* from 1979 and + *and* – from 1994, both can be interpreted as a reflection of Said's anxiety concerning the erasure and exclusion of the Palestinian presence and history. The earlier of these two works, *Self-Erasing Drawing* was made during Hatoum's student years and is Conceptual and Minimalist in style. The work is a small 28 by 28 cm square filled with sand. The kinetic object consists of a small rotating arm that concurrently draws lines in the sand with one side of its arm and then proceeds to erase them with the other. This process of mark making and consequent erasure results in an anticipation of the sand drawing's inevitable disappearance. The expression 'to draw a line in the sand' is to imply that a particular idea or indeed activity will not be supported or tolerated. To actively erase or refute this idea is to suggest that steadfastness can be overridden, and in the case of Hatoum's work, literally overwritten. The kinetic arm's process of erasure thus forges 'a sense of existence accentuated by a fear of disappearance'.^{xlv}

The latter version of Hatoum's sand drawing works, the much larger + *and* – from 1994, is, largely by virtue of its title, more actively connotative of Palestinian

history and experience. When one decides to approach + *and* – under what might be described as a Palestinian lens, the work becomes, as implied by its title, a discussion and representation of presence and absence. The dialectic between absence and presence is articulated through Edward Said's many remarks about the archival absence of the Palestinian presence and history just as it informs Carol Bardenstein's studies on the systematic Israeli campaign to erase the Palestinian physical and environmental presence. When one considers Bardenstein's studies in relationship to Hatoum's *Self-Erasing Drawing* and + *and* –, the marks made in both of Hatoum's kinetic works appear as though they're plough lines, ready made for the plantation of seeds, only to be swiftly erased as soon as they're created.

The Palestinian presence in historical Palestine is actively erased within the Israeli landscape. As an ideological and physical war over the land, the collective memories of both Palestinians and Israelis, are bound to the landscape. Consequently, there is constant antagonism between both their collective memories of and about the land. The omissive and destructive qualities of Jewish collective memory of the land over its Other (that is to say the Palestinian collective memory) have been widely written about by Carol Bardenstein. Bardenstein's studies focus on the landscape of Israel and the way that it has been systematically manipulated by both Israelis and Palestinians as a repository of both their collective memories.

Under Bardenstein's analysis, the Zionist ethos, 'a land without people for a people without land' has been projected onto the landscape of historical Palestine by the Jewish National Fund in a clear attempt to expunge the presence of the Other. The JNF is responsible for the plantation of several hundred million trees in Israel and in the

Occupied Palestinian Territories.^{xlvi} These JNF forests are a symbol of return for the Jewish people to their promised land of Israel and the transformation of the landscape is an assertion of their presence and return after generations in exile. As sites of cultural commemoration and memory, forests are transformed into an ideological battleground between Israelis and Palestinians over presence and remembrance in Israel. As a result of its tree planting activities over the sites of villages destroyed by the Zionist forces between 1947 and 1948 the JNF is a facilitator of a historical cover-up. The fund's widespread planting is an act that attempts to erase Palestinian collective memory of the landscape.^{xlvii} Though parred back and minimal, Hatoum's self-erasing sand works seem to tap into the history of Palestinian erasure within the landscape and may be interpreted as loaded minimal and conceptual works, operating and discussing in a sophisticated aesthetic language, the process of erasure of the Palestinian presence. Further still, it is as if Hatoum's kinetic machines concurrently reveal and erase Palestinian *sumud*.^{xlviii} The Palestinian steadfastness in the face of adversity, their metaphorical line in the sand is repeatedly destroyed and erased, only, like the prickly pear to re-surface over and over again.

The concern over the erasure of the Palestinian presence is also implicated in Hatoum's 1995 work *You Are Still Here*. The piece is a portrait-sized mirror with the words 'you are still here' etched into it. Curiously, when one looks at the work, there is a feeling of impossibility. Like an optical illusion one cannot simultaneously look at their reflection and read the text inscribed on the mirror. Our perceptions only allow us to do one or the other. Both activities, reading and viewing, nonetheless strive toward the same affirmation; a verification and assertion of presence. The subtle contours of

the inscribed text are not boldly visible. Verification and validation of presence, though achieved, is done with an element of strain and difficulty.

One might imagine Mona Hatoum looking into *You Are Still Here* and viewing her own reflection. One wonders what propels the artist to inscribe such a statement in their work. One might go so far as to ask, where is *here*? And why would my place and presence *here* ever be in such question that it requires to be stated and asserted. It is when one begins to ask these questions in reference to Hatoum's motivation for creating the work, that her background as a Palestinian begins to rise to the surface. Assuming Hatoum etched the mirror herself, one imagines the artist inscribing the four simple words into the mirror all the while faced with her own reflection. Like so many of Hatoum's works, *You Are Still Here* take its cue from Edward Said's seminal text, and is in itself a reflection on exile.

ⁱ Marianne Hirsch, *The Generation of Postmemory: Writing and Visual Culture After the Holocaust* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2012), 5.

ⁱⁱ Notable examples include the work of Kamal Boullata, Laura Marks and Ella Shohat. Kamal Boullata, *Palestinian Art: From 1850 to the Present* (London: Saqi, 2009), 176-178; Laura Marks, *The Skin of the Film, Intercultural Cinema, Embodiment, and the Senses* (Durham: Duke University Press, 2000), 153-156 and Ella Shohat, *Taboo Memories, Diasporic Voices* (Durham: Duke University Press, 2006), 308-312;

ⁱⁱⁱ Hamid Naficy, *An Accented Cinema: Exilic and Diasporic Filmmaking* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2001), 114.

^{iv} Mona Hatoum quoted in Michael Archer, Guy Brett and Cathering de Zegher, *Mona Hatoum* (London: Phaidon Press, 1996), 127.

^v Jill Bennett, *Empathic Vision: Affect, Trauma and Contemporary Art* (California: Stanford University Press, 2005), 143.

^{vi} Bennett, *Empathic Vision*, 143.

^{vii} Amal Amireh, "Between Complicity and Subversion: Body Politics in Palestinian National Narrative," *South Atlantic Quarterly*, no.102 (2003): 750.

^{viii} Notable examples include the work of Kamal Boullata, Amelia Jones and Marsha Meskimmon. Kamal Boullata, *Palestinian Art*; Amelia Jones ed., *The Feminism and Visual Culture Reader* (London; New York: Routledge, 2003) and Marsha Meskimmon, *Women Making Art: History, Subjectivity, Aesthetics* (London; New York: Routledge, 2003).

^{ix} Edward Said, "Emily Jacir – 'Where We Come From,'" in *Emily Jacir – Belongings*, Christian Kravagna, John Menick, Stella Rollig and Edward Said (Vienna: O.K Books, 2003) 47-48 and Edward Said, "Slow Death: Punishment by Detail," *From Oslo to Iraq and the Roadmap* (London: Bloomsbury Publishing, 2005), 94.

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- ^x Alon Confino, "Collective Memory and Cultural History: Problems of Method," *The American Historical Review*, no. 102 (1997): 1397.
- ^{xi} Boullata, *Palestinian Art*, 123-160.
- ^{xii} Kaja Silverman cited in Marianne Hirsch, *Family Frames: Photography, Narrative and Postmemory*, (Massachusetts: Harvard University Press, 1997), 22.
- ^{xiii} Hirsch, *Family Frames*, 22.
- ^{xiv} Karl Mannheim cited in Ruben Rumbaut, "Ages, Life Stages and Generational Cohorts: Decomposing the Immigrant First and Second Generations in the United States," *International Migration Review*, no. 38 (2004): 1162 and Rosemary Sayigh, "Palestinian Camp Women as Tellers of History," *Journal of Palestine Studies*, no. 27 (1998): 45.
- ^{xv} Lila Abu-Lughod, "Return to Half Ruins: Memory, Postmemory and living history in Palestine," in eds. Abu-Lughod and Ahmad H. Sa'adi, *Nakba: Palestine, 1948, and the Claims of Memory* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2007), 79.
- ^{xvi} Susan J. Brison, "Trauma Narratives and the Remaking of the Self," in *Acts of Memory: Cultural Recall in the Present*, Mieke Bal, Jonathan Crewe, Leo Spitzer, (Hanover: University Press of New England, 1999), 40.
- ^{xvii} Ilan Pappé, *A History of Modern Palestine: One Land, Two Peoples*, 2nd ed. (Cambridge Massachusetts: Cambridge University Press, 2006), xx; Tony Judt, "Introduction," in *From Oslo to Iraq and the Roadmap*, xviii and Marc H. Ellis and Daniel McGowan, *Remembering Deir Yassin: The Future of Israel and Palestine* (New York: Olive Branch Press, 1998), ix.
- ^{xviii} Susan Brison, "Trauma Narratives and the Remaking of the Self," in *Acts of Memory*, 40.
- ^{xix} Mahmoud Darwish, "We Walk Towards A Land," in *Sand and Other Poems*, trans. Rana Kabbani. (New York: Routledge, 1986), 3.
- ^{xx} Rosemary Sayigh, "Women's Nakba Stories: Between Being and Knowing," in *Nakba: Palestine, 1948, and the Claims of Memory*, eds., Abu-Lughod et al., 137.
- ^{xxi} Mikhail Bakhtin cited in Susan Slyomovics, *The Object of Memory: Arab and Jew Narrate the Palestinian Village* (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 1998), 207
- ^{xxii} Susan Slyomovics, "The Rape of Qula," in *Nakba: Palestine, 1948 and the Claims of Memory*, eds., Abu-Lughod et al., 32.
- ^{xxiii} Said K. Aburish, *Arafat: From Defender to Dictator* (London: Bloomsbury Publishing, 1999), 31.
- ^{xxiv} Brigitte L. Nacos, "The Portrayal of Female Terrorists in the Media: Similar Framing Patterns in the News Coverage of Women in Politics and Terrorism," *Studies in Conflict and Terrorism*, no. 28 (2005): 439. The individual most notably responsible for subverting the masculinity of the *keffiyeh* is the Palestinian female icon Leila Khaled.
- ^{xxv} Homi Bhabha, "Another Country," in *Without Boundary; Seventeen Ways of Looking*, ed. Fereshteh Daftari, (New York: The Museum of Modern Art, 2006), 34.
- ^{xxvi} Bhabha, "Another Country," 34.
- ^{xxvii} Mona Hatoum quoted in Laura Steward Heon, ed., *Mona Hatoum: Domestic Disturbance* (North Adams: Storey Books, 2001), 32.
- ^{xxviii} Gannit Ankori, *Palestinian Art*, (London: Reaktion Books, 2006), 137.
- ^{xxix} Ellis et al., *Remembering Deir Yassin*, vii.
- ^{xxx} Majid Al-Haj, "National Ethos, Multicultural Education and the New History Textbooks in Israel," *Curriculum Inquiry*, no. 5 (2005): 64. Al-Haj's study of history textbooks in Israeli schools documents the ways Israeli history textbooks differ from the Palestinian narrative of the event.
- ^{xxxi} Meir Pa'il quoted in Ellis and McGowan, *Remembering Deir Yassin*, 38. In interview with Daniel McGowan, Israeli military historian and retired member of the Israeli Defence Force, Colonial Meir Pa'il, discusses his involvement with the *Hagana* at the massacre of *Deir Yassin*.
- ^{xxxii} Pappé, *A History of Modern Palestine*, 128-130 and Nur-eldeen Masalha, "On Recent Hebrew and Israeli Sources for the Palestinian Exodus, 1947 – 1949," *Journal of Palestine Studies*, no. 18 (1998): 124. *Deir Yassin* was a consequence of *Plan Dalet*, a military blueprint co-ordinated by the *Hagana* (the Zionist military that eventually became the Israeli Defence Force), in anticipation of clashes with Arab forces in Palestine both before and after the foundation of Israel. As *Plan Dalet* was realised between April and May 1948, *Deir Yassin* was one of the first villages to be destroyed under the new military plan.
- ^{xxxiii} Menachim Begin quoted in Ellis et al., *Remembering Deir Yassin*, 3.

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- ^{xxxiv} Frances Hasso, "Modernity and Gender in Arab Accounts of the 1948 and 1967 Defeats," *International Journal of Middle Eastern Studies*, no. 32 (2000): 495.
- ^{xxxv} Hasso, "Modernity and Gender in Arab Accounts of the 1948 and 1967 Defeats," 495. Hasso notes that stories of Zionist attacks against women held particular pertinence to Muslim Palestinians, who viewed women's bodies as particularly vulnerable. The Muslim population considered sexual and physical attacks against women as prohibited even in warfare.
- ^{xxxvi} Haleem Eid quoted in *Deir Yassin Remembered*, "Survivor's Accounts.," <http://www.deiryassin.org/survivors.html> (accessed April 29 2012)
- ^{xxxvii} Hasso, "Modernity and Gender in Arab Accounts of the 1948 and 1967 Defeats," 495. The focus on the female body in the exodus of 1948, also extended to the nationalist movement in the early years following the *Nakba*. Historical Palestine was in these years often symbolised using the female figure. Importantly, as the loss of honour was seen as the instigator of the Palestinian exodus of 1948, the nationalist movement in the 1970s employed the new catchcry of 'land before honour', in order to counter weigh the effect of warfare tactics which would compromise honour.
- ^{xxxviii} Samera Esmeir, "Memories of Conquest: Witnessing Death in Tantura," in *Nakba: Palestine and the Claims of Memory*, eds. Abu-Lughod et al., 243.
- ^{xxxix} Mona Hatoum quoted in Archer et al., *Mona Hatoum*, 122.
- ^{xl} Mona Hatoum quoted in Archer et al., *Mona Hatoum*, 127
- ^{xli} Benny Morris, "The Historiography of Deir Yassin," *The Journal of Israeli History*, no. 24 (2005): 97.
- ^{xlii} Edward Said, "The Art of Displacement: Mona Hatoum's Logic of Irreconcilables," *Mona Hatoum: The Entire World as Foreign Land*, eds. Edward Said and Sheena Wagstaff (London: Tate Gallery Publishing, 2000), 7.
- ^{xliii} Yuko Hasegawa, *De-Genderism Detruire Dit-elle/ill* cited in Michael Brett, "Itinerary", in *Mona Hatoum*, Archer et al., 38.
- ^{xliv} Ellis et al., *Remembering Deir Yassin*, v–v1.
- ^{xlvi} Said, "Reflections on Exile," *Reflections on Exile and Other Essays* (Cambridge MA: Harvard University Press, 2002), 186. The phrase 'the entire world as a foreign land' comes from Edward Said's seminal essay *Reflections on Exile*. Said argues in the essay that it is the exile's awareness of simultaneous dimensions and their ability to move between cultures that informs their view of 'the entire world as a foreign land'.
- ^{xlvi} Carol Bardenstein, "Trees Forests and the Shaping of Palestinian and Israeli Collective Memory," in *Acts of Memory: Cultural Recall in the Present*, 158.
- ^{xlvi} Translating from the Arabic to mean 'steadfastness' or 'doggedness', *sumud* is used to describe the steadfastness of Palestinians against the adversity of exile, occupation and dispossession.